

INDUCING FAILURES IN COMPOSITE FLYWHEELS- A STUDY USING 3 POINT BENDING

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper we report on a study where many of the relevant loading conditions in a rotating flywheel are reproduced via 3 point bending tests on a model system. For this purpose coupon samples made up from a unidirectional, 24-ply, IM7/8552 carbon fibre composite material are tested in bend configurations. These coupons have been fabricated with a range of defects including a sharp transverse crack as well as specimens with internal delamination defects located at different plies within the stacking sequence.

The results report a much lower failure stress than quoted for the material, which is likely to stem from the complex stress situation at the load point. Crack propagation by both delamination and transverse cracking was observed, however the results indicated that transverse cracking only occurs when fibers are in compression, whilst delamination seems to occur much more readily when fibers are loaded in tension.

A finite element model was created to represent stresses within the coupon samples and interlaminar fracture properties of the matrix material were obtained experimentally to support further modelling work.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their high strength to density ratio, flywheels manufactured using carbon fibre composites have become a very feasible and effective method for short term energy storage. However, before composites can be used with confidence in this application, their potential failure mechanisms need to be further understood. In this work hand-laid up coupon samples are tested in a three-point bend configuration to replicate the stress conditions present in flywheels. Most composite flywheels are constructed from an inner steel hub and an outer composite rim with fibers aligned in the hoop direction [1]. When spun they will then be subjected to very high tensile hoop stresses and compressive radial stresses throughout. In addition the matrix material will be subjected to shear forces as the flywheel is spun up to speed and decelerated to a stationary state again [2, 3].

Figure 1: Normalized stress profiles for a flywheel with an inner steel rim and an outer composite part.

2 DESCRIPTION OF TEST SAMPLES

All tested samples are coupons of length 100mm, width 20mm and nominal thickness 3mm that have been produced from a Hexcel IM7/8552 pre-preg, cured at a temperature of 180 °C over a period of two hours. The lay-up is made from 24 plies where some specimens have a 5mm or 10mm wide and 13µm thick PTFE film inserted into the laminate at mid-length, centered to its mid-point at ply 4, 8 or 12. Others specimens have had a transverse crack of 1mm or 2mm depth inserted at the mid-length.

Engineering constant	unit	Identification as given by Hexcel data sheet
E_1	[GPa]	164
E_2, E_3	[GPa]	12
G_{12}	[GPa]	-
$\sigma_{11, \max}$ tensile	[MPa]	2724
$\sigma_{11, \max}$ compr	[MPa]	1690
$\tau_{12, \max}$	[MPa]	120

Table 1: Properties for the Hexcel IM7/8552 composite used.

Figure 2a: Schematic of delamination defect placement.

Figure 2b: Schematic of transverse defect placement.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PLANNING

For the bend testing ASTM standard D790 [4] and ISO-14125 standard [5] have been employed.

3.1 Three point bending - Flexural Strength testing; no defects present.

An in-house manufactured three-point bend rig with a centrally mounted extensometer/deflectometer plunger combination was used throughout the tests. To determine the flexural strength of the laminate, tests were conducted at a number of different span lengths ranging from 50mm to 80mm. This is because for specimens with a high thickness to span length ratio the contributions of both shear and axial forces to deflection have to be taken into account. Each flexural test was performed three times with the central loading on both the top and bottom faces of the specimen. The results were then taken from the average of those three tests.

The central deflection due to both bending and shear forces [6] are given in Equation 1. From this equation an expression giving the apparent flexural modulus and including both shear and axial contributions to total deflection can be obtained such as given in Equation 2. System compliance doesn't need to be accounted for as extensometer readings rather than crosshead displacements were used to obtain central deflection and the lower supports are assumed infinitely rigid.

$$\delta = \frac{PL^3}{4bd^3E} + \frac{3PL}{8bdG} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{E'_b} = \frac{1}{E_b} + \frac{3d^2}{2L^2 G} \quad (2)$$

Here δ is the central beam displacement, P is the applied force, b , d and E are specimen width, thickness and tensile modulus respectively, G is the specimens shear modulus and E'_b is the apparent flexural modulus as a given specimen length. The true flexural modulus E_b can be obtained by plotting $1/E'_b$ against d^2/L^2 , such that a linear plot governed by Equation 3 can be obtained

$$\frac{1}{E'_b} = \frac{1}{E_b} + \frac{3m}{2G} \quad \text{where } m = \frac{d^2}{L^2} \quad (3)$$

3.2 Three point bending – Destructive testing; defects now present

For the destructive testing a camera was added to the experimental setup, such that the sequence of damage occurings could be recorded. To provide additional insight into the failure mechanisms, optical microscopy was carried out on all samples tested up to the point of fracture. Unless stated otherwise at least five specimens of each type were tested. Using the formulas provided by the standard document [7] both maximum fiber stress and maximum fiber strain could be calculated for both the onset of yielding and at the maximum ultimate load.

4 RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

4.1 Three point bending - Flexural Strength testing

The results obtained for the apparent flexural moduli for the specimen were inverted and plotted against $m = d^2/L^2$ such that a results for the true flexural modulus could be obtained by extrapolation such as shown in Figure 3. Here three separate lines are shown. The red data points refer to specimens that have been tested with the top face up; the blue ones refer to those tested with the bottom side facing up. Finally the green data points give an average value of both these and were used to obtain the flexural modulus.

Figure 3: Linear plot used to determine elastic material properties

When using the average value, a true flexural modulus of 164 GPa with a standard deviation of 16 GPa is obtained. This value exactly matches the value for the materials young's modulus quoted by the manufacturer (Table 1).

4.2 Three point bending – Destructive testing

Results for both maximum fiber stresses and strains have been summarized in Table 2 whilst the remainder of this section will focus on reporting on failure mechanisms and fractography throughout these tests.

Sample defect	Intact	Transverse defect		Delamination defect	
	none	1mm, transverse	2mm, transvers	5mm, Ply 8	10mm, Ply 4
$\sigma_{f, \text{onset}}$	1331.1	640.6	-	1332.7	1331.7
error	± 83.3	± 47.2	-	± 61.5	± 34.2
$\epsilon_{f, \text{onset}}$	8.9	6.2	-	9.3	7.7
error	± 0.4	± 1.0	-	± 0.7	± 5.3
$\sigma_{f, \text{max}}$	1350.3	1474.2	762.6	1365.0	1341.4
error	± 83.3	± 106.1	± 70.2	± 48.4	± 15.8
$\epsilon_{f, \text{max}}$	9.9	16.4	13.8	10.8	7.7
error	± 0.6	± 0.5	± 0.7	± 1.0	± 5.3

Table 2: Maximum fiber stress and strain at both onset of damage and maximum load sustained. Stress values are given in MPa

Specimen without defects

When testing intact specimens all specimens failed in flexure. One specimen also showed a large delamination site. The other specimens exhibited local fiber-pull-out or de-bonding, most commonly at the outer edges. It was also observed, that specimens showed a tendency to fail above the neutral axis where compressive stress existed. For several specimens a large delamination between the compressive and tensile regions was observed.

The failed specimen exhibited two distinct fracture surfaces depending on whether tensile or compressive failure occurred. The tensile surface shows a lot of pulled out fibres. The compressed surface looks comparatively shiny.

Figure 4: Microscopy of sample, front view

Figure 5: Microscopy of the fracture surfaces from, viewed from centre

Transverse crack – 1mm

The first two specimens were tested with the transverse notch located on the tensile face resulting in delamination initiating from the notch tip at load of 300N such as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Onset of a first delamination defect, sample G16

The remaining specimens were tested with the notch located on the compressive surface and transverse crack propagation led to ultimate flexural failure. Here both a delamination and a transverse defect grew from the initial defect and fracture occurs. Throughout this process fibre fracture, matrix cracking and delamination onset occur within the specimen, especially in the tensile regions such as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: LHS - load deflection trace for a 1mm transverse defect
RHS - optical post-failure microscopy for this specimen

Figure 8: Optical microscopy of the cross-section of the specimen

Transverse crack – 2mm

Similar results were obtained for the 2mm transverse defects except that failure occurred at significantly lower load than for the specimens with 1mm transverse defects.

Delamination defect – 5mm, ply 8

Three out of the five specimens failed due to a sudden delamination along the defect (ply 8) plane which perforates across the whole specimen. Other defect modes were random delamination onsets throughout the specimen and transverse cracking in the upper (compressed) region of the sample. The two remaining samples also failed due to abrupt delamination that simultaneously occurred in different locations, the most significant delamination occurring at ply 8.

For those specimens, the first damage visible was a transverse crack in the central region however the sample failed in rapid delamination.

Figure 9: Specimen B02 (ply 8, 5mm defect) first transverse crack growth & final failure mechanism

Figure 10: LHS - Load vs. deflection graph; RHS - optical post-failure microscopy

As shown in the load deflection graph in Figure 10 the yield stress was very close to the maximum stress reached. Following the onset of yielding the load required to sustain the applied strain rate fluctuates, indicating energy dissipation, until final failure occurs by delamination.

The optical microscopy shown in Figure 10 confirms that the final delamination runs across ply 8, where the defect was also embedded. Both transverse cracking and delamination are present within the specimen, however the ultimate failure mechanisms for this set was delamination.

Delamination defect – ply 4, 10mm

For most specimens the stress experienced at the onset of yielding was also the maximum stress reached and following that the load required to sustain the strain rate continuously decreased. All

specimens tested in this set failed due to a combination of transverse cracking and delamination with delamination being the ultimate cause of failure. Transverse cracking tended to occur first in the upper, compressed section of the specimen. Eventually transverse crack growth stalls around ply 6-8 and the crack propagates by delamination such as shown in Figure 11. However, no crack growth along the defect site at ply 4 occurs and this site does not contribute to the failure mechanism.

Figure 11: Crack propagation and optical microscopy for a 10mm insert at ply 4.

5 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Finite element models using the Abaqus 6.12 software have been developed to more fully understand the stress conditions in the test specimens. To accurately model crack initiation due to delamination for the specimens with insert defects a cohesive zone model was used. For this interlaminar fracture toughness values are required.

5.1 Interlaminar fracture toughness characterization

Interlaminar fracture toughness characterization was carried out on a unidirectional AS4/8552 Hexcel composite. This material has the same matrix material and fiber volume fraction as the composite tested in three-point bending. Fracture toughness values were obtained by means of the DCB[8], C-ELS[9] and FRMM[10] tests. At least 5 specimens were tested in each of these configurations and errors were computed using the standard deviation across specimens. Results obtained are summarized in Table 3 and a Mixed Mode I/II failure locus is shown in Figure 12. The FRMM test has a Mode I/II ratio of 4/3 so that a Mode I component of 251 J/m² and a Mode II component of 188 J/m² were obtained.

Test configuration	G _{IC/IIc} component obtained	
	value	error
Mode I DCB	249 J/m ²	±24 J/m ²
Mode II ELS	722 J/m ²	±101 J/m ²
Mixed Mode I/II FRMM	439 J/m ²	±39 J/m ²

Table 3: Summary of fracture toughness values obtained for AS4/8552 Hexcel composite

5.2 Development of FE Model

To maximize computational efficiency it was decided to use a two-dimensional model and only half the test specimen was modelled and an axisymmetric boundary condition was specified across the specimen centre. Young's and Shear moduli were sourced from the 3PB flexural strength tests represented in Sections 3.1 and 4.1 of this paper. Maximum tensile, compressive and shear stresses were sourced from the Hexcel datasheet and interlaminar fracture toughness properties were obtained from the work outlined in Section 5.1.

Two separate parts were used for the top and the bottom regions of the sample such that the corresponding crack initiation load for a delamination in between the plies could be determined using a cohesive zone model applied at the surfaces in between the parts. The load was applied by fixing the nodes at the support span points and applying a ramped displacement boundary condition to the node

located at the load nose. Both a schematic of the model and the FE result for the intact specimen are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Mixed Mode I/II failure locus from AS4/8552 fracture toughness characterization

Figure 13: schematic of FE model (LHS) and viewport showing the FEA field output for σ_{11} .

A mesh sensitivity analysis was carried out and the optimum element size was determined to be 0.5mm. When further decreasing element size to 0.25mm results obtained would deviate by less than 1% whilst computational cost would be significantly increased.

5.3 Comparison of FE model and experimental data

The final element model for the intact specimen was run for the various span lengths at which flexural strength testing was conducted and both load and central deflection outputs were extracted from the FE output. This permits a direct comparison of results obtained by numerical analysis and experimental research, such as shown in Table 4 below.

Method	$E_{\text{apparent}}/\text{GPa}$ for each value of span length							$E_{\text{true}}/\text{GPa}$
	50mm	55mm	60mm	65mm	70mm	75mm	80mm	
Experimental	122.94	124.14	134.65	136.68	137.72	142.75	144.72	164
error	± 8.68	± 8.09	± 8.16	± 7.76	± 7.36	± 7.22	± 6.96	
Numerical	128.32	133.36	137.47	140.84	143.64	145.98	147.96	164
error	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 4: Comparison of experimental and analytical results for the intact specimen

Both the experimental measurements and the numerical model give similar results, indicating that the FE model provides an accurate analysis of the loading conditions. However the FE model was less

sensitive to a change in span length indicating that at present shear forces may not be represented accurately.

5.4 Planned future FE work

The aim of future FE work will be to modify this model to account for delamination stemming from inserted defects by means of a cohesive zone model and to predict at what load a delamination due to such a defect would propagate.

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Three-point bending – Flexural Strength testing

The flexural testing was used to measure the flexural modulus of the composite material tested and was obtained using the gradient of the load vs. deflection curve when loading the specimen up to 300N. The flexural modulus obtained was found to be in very close agreement with the value quoted in the manufacturer's data sheet, indicating that the measurement of the load and deflection of the specimen were performed to good accuracy.

6.2 Three-point bending – Destructive testing

Defect-free specimens were tested in flexure to destruction. The values of the average maximum fibre yield stress and (ultimate) failure stress were measured to be 1331 MPa and 1350 MPa respectively. Both of these values were lower than quoted in the manufacturer's data sheet which gives tensile and compressive strengths of 2724 MPa and 1690 MPa respectively. It is probable that this arises due to the complex stress situation at the central load point. Post-failure microscopy of the test specimens shows two distinct fracture surfaces, a compressive failure surface on the top part of the specimen and a tensile failure surface on the lower part of the specimen. The fracture surface from the part of the specimen subjected to tension appeared to be more prone to fibre pull-out and local delamination. There was a tendency for a large delamination to form in between the tensile and compressive regions. The final failure mechanism observed was flexural failure.

Testing of specimens containing a 1mm translaminar defect revealed that locating the crack in the tensile rather than the compressive region of the specimen resulted in delamination initiating from the tip of the notch. The un-notched section of the specimen was subjected to bending, whilst the fibres across the notch that do not carry any load stay straight. This causes high shear forces at the tip of the notch which results in a delamination initiating.

The specimens for which a 1mm translaminar defect was placed in the compressive region of the specimen failed in flexure. For these specimens a yield stress of 641 MPa and a maximum (failure) stress of 1474 MPa were measured.

The specimens containing a 2mm translaminar defect (in the compressive region) failed by flexure and a maximum failure stress of 763MPa was measured.

The specimens containing a central delamination defect of 5mm in length located at the 8th ply of the stacking sequence exhibited failure by initially a translaminar crack growing in the compressive section of the specimen but then final failure occurring due to delamination from the defect film. The original translaminar defect initiated at around 1333 MPa and the delamination was induced and rapidly propagated at 1365 MPa. The failure sequence was confirmed by observations during the test and subsequent optical microscopy of the specimen.

Testing of the specimens containing a central delamination defect of 10mm in length located at the 4th ply of the stacking sequence exhibited failure by initially a translaminar crack occurring together with delamination in the upper (compressive) part of the specimen followed by ultimate failure by delamination at ply 8. Thus the site of the final delamination failure was away from the plane of the inserted defect. The original translaminar defect initiated at 1332 MPa and the final delamination was induced at 1341 MPa. The failure sequence was confirmed again by observations during the test and subsequent optical microscopy of the specimen.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Composite beam specimens with no defects and with inserted defects in either the transverse or interlaminar regions were tested to failure in 3-point bending. Both intact specimens and specimens with a transverse defect failed in flexure, whilst those with insert defects failed in delamination. The observation of failure mechanisms showed that regions with fibers loaded under tensile forces are much more susceptible to matrix cracking, fibre pull-out and delamination than those with fibers subjected to compressive loading. When the fibers are subjected to compressive loading transverse cracking becomes the dominant failure mechanism.

A finite element model was employed to predict the stresses within the test specimens. Interlaminar fracture properties of the material were determined experimentally such that the onset of delamination due to an insert defect can be implemented into future modelling work.

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